

Structure solution of protein complex ALK2/FKBP12 with PK010710 and PK012055

Data collected at the Diamond Light source, beamline I03 on 4th May 2018.

XX10ACVR1A-d001 x014 (PK010710)

Data processed using IMOSFLM before scaling using Aimless and Pointless. Space group P21 21 21 determined with one complex in the unit cell.

Phasing done using Phenix Phaser using 3H9R (FKBP12 with ACVR1A and Dorsomorphin) as a model (water and ligand removed).

Ligand built using Phenix eLBOW

Model building done in Coot.

Refinement done using Phenix Refine.

04-05-2018 22:57:17 - XX10ACVR1A/XX10ACVR1A-x007/XX10ACVR1A-x007_3_####.cbf	
Sample: XX10ACVR1A-x007	Flux: 1.49e+12
Ω Start: 147.0°	Ω Osc: 0.15°
Ω Overlap: 0°	No. Images: 1200
Resolution: 1.60Å	Wavelength: 0.9763Å
Exposure: 0.050s	Transmission: 100.00%
Beamsize: 80x20µm	Type: SAD
Comment: (703,-451,-228) Aperture: Large	

XX10ACVR1A-d002 x007 (PK012055)

Data processed using IMOSFLM before scaling using Aimless and Pointless. Space group P21 21 21 determined with one complex in the unit cell.

Phasing done using CCP4 Phaser MR using 3H9R (FKBP12 with ACVR1A and Dorsomorphin) as a model (water and ligand removed).

Ligand built using Phenix eLBOW

Model building done in Coot.

Refinement done using Phenix Refine.

04-05-2018 23:10:13 - XX10ACVR1A/XX10ACVR1A-x014/XX10ACVR1A-x014_2_####.cbf	
Sample: XX10ACVR1A-x014	Flux: 1.51e+12
Ω Start: 147.0°	Ω Osc: 0.15°
Ω Overlap: 0°	No. Images: 1200
Resolution: 1.40Å	Wavelength: 0.9763Å
Exposure: 0.050s	Transmission: 100.00%
Beamsize: 80x20µm	Type: SAD
Comment: (1037,-601,-157) Aperture: Large	